

1 **Systematic discovery of cell and immune function in IBD: Chemokines.**

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6 **Chemokines**

7 a. CXCL11

8 i. Activated by MDP in wild-type monocytes

9 ii. Activation by MDP is completely lost in CD patient NOD2 mutants

10 b. CCL22

11 i. Activation by MDP in wild-type monocytes but this is lost in CD patient NOD2 monocytes

12 Citations

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18 Moder, S., Thaler, R., Eiber, S. and Meyer, B., 2019. CCL22 controls immunity by promoting regulatory T
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